

Factors Influencing Property Values in Gated and Non-Gated Estates

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Abstract

The aim of the study is to compare residential property values between gated and non-gated estates in Abuja, Nigeria with a view to providing information that will enhance investment decision-making; assessed the physical features of both estate types; and explore factors influencing property values. Data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to estate firms and residents using simple random sampling. Out of 218 questionnaires given to firms, 156 were retrieved, while 213 were recovered from 320 distributed to residents. The study utilized the use of frequency distribution table, mean score analysis and factor analysis using factor analysis, the study findings show clear contrasts between the factors influencing residential preferences in gated and non-gated communities. In gated communities, the leading factors are controlled access and exclusive services, socioeconomic profile of residents and social status or prestige, emphasizing security, exclusivity and social class. In non-gated communities, however, neighborhood crime rates, market demand and resident demographics are most significant, highlighting concerns for safety, affordability and accessibility. The study recommends that policymakers and investors consider macroeconomic indicators such as inflation, living costs and post-pandemic population shifts when making decisions related to residential real estate. Overall, gated communities exhibit more stable and higher valuation outcomes, especially for two- and three-bedroom flats, reflecting their appeal among security-conscious and economically empowered residents.

Keywords: Comparative Analysis, Gated and Non-gated, Residential Property, Values and Abuja.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Gated and non-gated communities are the two main categories into which residential estates fall. Each has a distinct function in urban development and appeals to a range of consumer preferences. Non-gated estates, which place more emphasis on open access and community interaction, are very different from gated communities, which are distinguished by limited access, security elements and a high degree of exclusivity. Gated communities' private government methods and physical barriers serve inhabitants who seek privacy, security and consistent aesthetic standards, all of which tend to increase property prices in these communities (Allenand & Fraser, 2022; Turnbull & Velma, 2019). Non-gated estates, characterized by open accessibility, accommodate a wider socio-economic demographic and promote increased social interaction and inclusivity. These estates typically offer more

affordable housing options, as they do not incur additional homeowners association fees for security and private infrastructure maintenance (Akinde, 2018; Towart, & Ruming, 2022)

The lack of physical barriers in non-gated estates is consistent with a community development approach that values public accessibility and inclusion. Grundström and Celévrier (2023) revealed that unlike gated communities which frequently function as closed-off "consumption clubs," non-gated estates are incorporated into the larger urban fabric, providing open access to infrastructure such as parks, schools and public transit systems. This accessibility is especially useful for middle- and lower-income members, as non-gated communities often do not charge HOA fees, making them more inexpensive (Al-Shawabkeh et al., 2020). Furthermore, non-gated estates can generate better social cohesiveness by minimizing socioeconomic differences and fostering contacts across different demographic groups, resulting in a more integrated urban neighborhood (Che-Saari et al., 2020).

Despite these advantages, non-gated communities may have difficulty sustaining property prices in comparison to gated estates owing to their open openness. Wang et al., (2021), lack of controlled access might increase vulnerability to crime, which some studies show may result in decreased property values over time compared to gated communities. Non-gated estates, on the other hand, can minimize this by integrating with larger public services such as local enforcement and urban planning projects to improve infrastructure and public safety.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Residential property values represent the monetary worth of residential properties, encompassing tangible attributes like the physical structure and land and intangible aspects such as location desirability and access to amenities. This concept is pivotal in understanding real estate markets, urban planning dynamics and investment decision-making.

The physical characteristics of gated and non-gated estates have been extensively studied to understand their implications on community dynamics, security and accessibility. Similarly, Khoshnaw (2023) analyzed the physical and morphological characteristics of gated and non-gated neighborhoods in Gurugram, India, with an emphasis on urban planning challenges using observational methods and morphological analysis as the research identified that gated communities typically feature well-defined perimeters, restricted access points and homogeneous architectural styles. Adegun et al., (2021), in their study revealed that, non-gated

neighborhoods were characterized by organic growth patterns and mixed-use spaces. The findings of the study emphasized the impact of gating on urban planning policies and the physical form of neighborhoods.

Yang (2021) using case studies and a review of planning documents, the study highlighted the negative consequences of improperly controlled gated developments, including conflicts with local authorities and diminished community accessibility. The findings emphasized the need for applying Crime Prevention through Environmental Design (CPTED) principles to balance security with inclusivity. Aliu (2021) conducted a proximity-based social network analysis to compare co-presence patterns in gated and non-gated housing areas in Wuhan, China.

On the other hand, proximity to green spaces and waterfronts generally enhances property values, especially in gated communities where aesthetics and recreational amenities are prioritized. In many high-end gated estates, developers invest significantly in creating visually appealing environments with parks, water features and tree-lined streets. These elements not only improve the living experience but also contribute to higher property valuations by catering to the preferences of environmentally conscious buyers (Aliu, 2021). In broader view, a research analyzed the influence of urban rail transit on real estate values in China using mathematical modeling, the study demonstrated that proximity to transit systems positively correlated with property values (Tang, Li & Fan, 2022).

AlAmeri (2023), studied in UAE carried out a research on factors influencing property values, identifying market conditions, regulatory frameworks and amenities as critical determinants. Intrinsic property characteristics, such as building materials, design and amenities, are crucial to understanding variations in property values. Aliu (2021) surveyed estate firms in order to study the factors influencing residential property values and found that construction quality, potential for rental growth and structural attributes significantly influenced capital values in Abuja, Nigeria (Bello, Adepoju & Durosinmi, 2020).

Soyeh, Asabere and Owusu-Ansah (2020), expressed that one of the most prominent themes across the literature is the impact of security and exclusivity on property values, particularly in gated communities. Aliu (2021) demonstrated that gated estates in Accra, Ghana, command a significant price premium of 42–48% for sales and 48% for rentals compared to non-gated properties. In Nigeria, flooding is a recurring issue that affects both gated and non-gated estates. Furthermore, Abere, Ogunba & Dugeri (2020) in their studies revealed properties located in flood-prone

areas tend to experience depreciated values due to the associated risks and recurring maintenance costs. This is particularly problematic in non-gated estates, where drainage systems are often inadequate or poorly maintained, exacerbating the impact of flooding on property values.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the survey research method as its design framework. The research population of study includes Two Hundred and Eighteen (218) registered Estate Surveying and Valuation firms in Abuja and Three Hundred and Twenty (320) residential properties, which was selected as sample size using simple random sampling techniques. Descriptive statistics (frequency distribution Table and factor analysis) a technique for data reduction, was utilized to analyze the data. This method identifies a limited number of factors that can explain a larger set of observed data. It simplifies the complexity in data by revealing the underlying structure, thereby aiding in the interpretation of data with greater ease. It is a technique of analysis utilized to establish which of the variables could be measuring aspects of the same underlying dimensions.

Factor analysis extracts the maximum common variance from all variables and puts them into a common score (Huh, 2017). It proves efficient in identifying clusters of related variables and is ideal for minimizing an expansive number of variables into a more easily understood framework. Mathematically, the procedure assumes that an $n \times n$ matrix "A" has eigenvalues " λ " if there exists a non-zero vector "X", called an eigenvector associated with λ , for which:

$$Ax = \lambda x \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

From equation 1, it follows that the matrix $\{A - \lambda I\}$ is singular and therefore:

$$\text{Det}(A - \lambda I) = 0 \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Equation 2 is a polynomial equation in λ of degree "n" from which it follows that A is at most "n" eigenvalues. The polynomial $\text{Det}(A - \lambda I)$ is the characteristic polynomial of "A".

4.0 DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The physical characteristics of both gated and non-gated residential estates in Abuja were evaluated based on their presence or absence, utilizing frequency tables to present the findings and also the factors influencing property values in both gated and non-gated estate.

4.1 Physical Characteristics of Gated and Non-Gated Residential Estates

By examining key attributes such as controlled access points, security infrastructure, amenities and maintenance quality, the research highlights the disparities between gated estates, which typically offer enhanced security and exclusive facilities and non-gated estates, which rely more heavily on public infrastructure and services. The result is shown in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Physical Characteristics of Gated Residential Estates

Physical Characteristics	Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Controlled Access Points	Present	82	97.62
	Absent	2	2.38
	Total	84	100.00
Perimeter Fencing/Walls	Present	84	100.00
	Absent	0	0.00
	Total	84	100.00
Security Infrastructure	Present	78	92.86
	Absent	6	7.14
	Total	84	100.00
Private Roads and Streets	Present	80	95.24
	Absent	4	4.76
	Total	84	100.00
Amenities	Present	65	77.38
	Absent	19	22.62
	Total	84	100.00
Landscaping and Open Spaces	Present	75	89.29
	Absent	9	10.71
	Total	84	100.00
Street Lighting	Present	77	91.67
	Absent	7	8.33
	Total	84	100.00
Property Layout and Design	Present	76	90.48
	Absent	8	9.52
	Total	84	100.00

Parking and Vehicle Management	Present	79	94.05
	Absent	5	5.59
	Total	84	100.00
Maintenance and Cleanliness	Present	72	85.71
	Absent	12	14.29
	Total	84	100.00
Central Sewage Management	Present	77	91.67
	Absent	7	8.33
	Total	84	100.00

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2025.

Controlled access points are present in 97.62% of the surveyed estates, with only 2.38% lacking this feature. Jegede, Ibem and Oluwatayo (2020) affirmed that the physical layout and entry mechanisms of estates significantly shape residents' security perception, which in turn influences satisfaction and property desirability. The data show that perimeter fencing or walls are present in all 84 estates surveyed, representing 100% adoption.

Security infrastructure, including surveillance systems, security personnel, or alarm systems, is present in 92.86% of estates. Obi et al., (2023) findings noted that estates that offer robust security features tend to attract premium valuation due to the assurance they provide, especially in high-risk urban centers. Private roads and streets are a feature in 95.24% of the estates, indicating a commitment to independent internal mobility infrastructure. Amenities such as recreational facilities, pools, or gyms are present in 77.38% of the estates.

Landscaping and open spaces are incorporated into 89.29% of estates. As such, their presence correlates positively with valuation metrics, particularly in mid- to high-income developments. Street lighting, a fundamental infrastructure for safety and nighttime visibility, is present in 91.67% of the estates. According Isaac et al., (2019), explained adequate street lighting was a significant predictor of resident satisfaction and property safety perception in Northern Nigeria, thus justifying its strong impact on value appraisal in gated environments.

Regarding property layout and design, 90.48% of estates display organized design elements, such as road networks, plot alignment and housing typology. The 9.52% of estates without such defined layouts may suffer diminished appeal or require remedial planning to compete in the property value market. Parking and vehicle management features are present in 94.05% of

the estates, signifying a strong emphasis on functional vehicular infrastructure. Maintenance and cleanliness practices are actively implemented in 85.71% of the estates, a factor that reflects the long-term sustainability and desirability of a property. Central sewage management is a near-standard feature in Abuja's gated residential estates, present in 91.67% of surveyed properties.

Table 4.2: Physical Characteristics of Non-Gated Residential Estates

Physical Characteristics	Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Controlled Access Points	Present	0	0.00
	Absent	139	100.00
	Total	139	100.00
Perimeter Fencing/Walls	Present	98	70.50
	Absent	41	29.50
	Total	139	100.00
Security Infrastructure	Present	83	59.71
	Absent	56	40.29
	Total	139	100.00
Private Roads and Streets	Present	13	9.35
	Absent	126	90.65
	Total	139	100.00
Amenities	Present	56	40.29
	Absent	83	59.71
	Total	139	100.00
Landscaping and Open Spaces	Present	98	70.50
	Absent	41	29.50
	Total	139	100.00
Street Lighting	Present	117	84.17
	Absent	22	15.83
	Total	139	100.00
Property Layout and Design	Present	111	79.86
	Absent	28	20.14
	Total	139	100.00
Parking and Vehicle Management	Present	70	50.36

	Absent	69	49.64
	Total	139	100.00
Maintenance and Cleanliness	Present	83	59.71
	Absent	56	40.29
	Total	139	100.00
Central Sewage Management	Present	97	69.78
	Absent	42	30.22
	Total	139	100.00

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2025.

Perimeter fencing or walls were present in 70.50% of the estates, while 29.50% had no such boundaries. Security infrastructure ranging from local vigilante services to CCTV was present in 59.71% of the estates. However, 40.29% remained without any security mechanisms in place. Private roads and internal street networks were among the least available features, with only 9.35% of the estates having such infrastructure. The overwhelming reliance on public roads by 90.65% of the estates is a clear indicator of infrastructural insufficiency. Musah et al., (2021) revealed that inadequate road planning in residential areas contributed to increased vulnerability to burglary and urban blight, especially where long, unlit, or poorly maintained roads created crime-prone corridors.

Amenities such as recreational areas, water points and communal spaces were present in only 40.29% of the estates, with the majority 59.71% having no such shared facilities. The presence of landscaping and open spaces in 70.50% of the estates offers a contrastingly optimistic view. Street lighting was the most consistently provided infrastructure, with 84.17% of estates featuring it. Property layout and design were evident in 79.86% of the estates. Nwaogu (2021) noted that properties located in estates with formal layouts consistently outperform others in terms of market price appreciation. The 20.14% of estates lacking this characteristic likely suffer from congestion, accessibility issues and informal expansion conditions known to limit value appreciation and regulatory compliance.

Parking and vehicle management were equally split, with 50% of estates having some form of structured parking and the other half lacking it. Maintenance and cleanliness were reported in 59.71% of the estates, with 40.29% showing no indication of ongoing upkeep. Central sewage management is present in approximately 70% of non-gated residential estates in Abuja,

indicating its significant but not universal adoption across the 139 surveyed properties. However, the 30.22% of estates lacking this feature, likely relying on septic tanks, may face reduced desirability and valuation due to potential maintenance challenges and perceived inferiority, highlighting a key disparity in infrastructure that impacts market competitiveness within Abuja's non-gated residential landscape.

4.2 Factors Influencing Property Values in Gated and Non-Gated Estates

Respondents, who were the practicing estate surveying and valuation firms, were asked to indicate their level of agreement with a series of statements using the following scale: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Somewhat Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1); and the data was analyzed on IBM SPSS GUI using Factor Analysis (Principal Component Analysis).

Table 4.3: Descriptive Analysis of the Factors Influencing Property Values in Gated Residential Estates

Factors	Mean	Rank
Controlled Access and Exclusive Services	3.8344	1 st
Socioeconomic Profile of Residents	3.8344	2 nd
Perceived Social Status and Prestige	3.8217	3 rd
Higher demand for gated communities in urban areas	3.8025	4 th
Street and Road Conditions	3.7134	5 th
Regulatory compliance in construction practices	3.6879	6 th
Availability of Technology and Connectivity	3.6433	7 th
Availability and Quality of Infrastructure	3.5669	8 th
Supply and Demand Dynamics	3.5605	9 th
Aesthetic Appeal and Environmental Quality	3.5541	10 th
Higher Service Charges	3.5414	11 th
Community Initiatives	3.4713	12 th
Accessibility to major roads and public transportation networks	3.4713	13 th
Design and Physical Characteristics of Properties	3.4459	14 th
Urban Planning and Land-Use Policies	3.4459	15 th
Public Infrastructure and Service Quality	3.4331	16 th
Flexibility in Land Use and Modifications	3.4268	17 th
Neighborhood Crime Rates	3.4204	18 th

Diversity and Heterogeneity of Residents	3.2885	19 th
Flood Risk and Climate Vulnerability	3.2102	20 th

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2025.

The highest-ranked factor, with a mean score of 3.8344, is Controlled Access and Exclusive Services. Equally ranked in second place is the Socioeconomic Profile of Residents (mean = 3.8344). Following closely is Perceived Social Status and Prestige (mean = 3.8217), which indicates that symbolic and reputational elements of gated estates such as branding, visual aesthetics and elitist identity carry considerable weight in influencing property values. This supports assertion that aspirational lifestyle perceptions increasingly drive valuation metrics, especially in high-end urban markets (Agava, & Gamu, 2024).

The fourth-ranked factor, Higher Demand for Gated Communities in Urban Areas (mean = 3.8025). Medale and Ezeokoli (2023) as found in the study by upward price trends are closely associated with the limited availability and high demand for secure housing formats in Nigeria's major urban centers. Fifth on the list is Street and Road Conditions (mean = 3.7134), an indicator that property accessibility and internal mobility still hold considerable influence. Regulatory Compliance in Construction Practices (mean = 3.6879) ranks sixth, showing that buyers and investors value legal integrity and adherence to zoning and safety codes. This resonates with research by who emphasized that adherence to official land-use regulations and construction standards affects long-term valuation by minimizing the risk of property devaluation due to policy enforcement or demolition actions (Obed-Ndukwu, Ayotamuno, & Chukwuemeka, 2020).

In seventh place, Availability of Technology and Connectivity (mean = 3.6433), Availability and Quality of Infrastructure (mean = 3.5669) is eighth, reflecting foundational issues such as water supply, drainage and power. Medale and Ezeokoli (2023) explained that inadequate or inconsistent infrastructure often leads to value suppression, particularly in less formal gated estate. The ninth-ranked factor, Supply and Demand Dynamics (mean = 3.5605), reinforces how property valuation in gated estates is not just about intrinsic features but also market fluctuations. At tenth place is Aesthetic Appeal and Environmental Quality (mean = 3.5541), higher service charges (mean = 3.5414), ranked eleventh, represents a double-edged factor.

Community Initiatives and Accessibility to Major Roads and Public Transportation both hold a mean score of 3.4713, ranking twelfth and thirteenth respectively. Ranked fourteenth is

Design and Physical Characteristics of Properties (mean = 3.4459), including layout, floor area and construction quality. Equal in score and rank is Urban Planning and Land-Use Policies (mean = 3.4459), suggesting that while regulatory frameworks matter, their direct effect on valuation may be less perceptible to homeowners unless tied to enforcement outcomes.

Public Infrastructure and Service Quality follows closely in sixteenth place (mean = 3.4331), emphasizing that government-provided services like schools, hospitals and roads contribute to area attractiveness but may be undercut by the self-sufficient nature of many gated communities. Flexibility in Land Use and Modifications (mean = 3.4268), ranked seventeenth, shows limited relevance in gated communities where strict covenants often restrict modifications to maintain uniformity thus, reducing its impact on valuation.

Neighborhood Crime Rates (mean = 3.4204) is ranked eighteenth, somewhat surprisingly low given that security is a major selling point of gated estates. Diversity and Heterogeneity of Residents (mean = 3.2885), at nineteenth, suggests that homogeneity is often more valued in these enclaves, which is consistent with who found that socioeconomic similarity often enhances community trust and stability. Finally, the lowest-ranked factor, Flood Risk and Climate Vulnerability (mean = 3.2102), underscores an alarming undervaluation of climate risk in property decisions.

Table 4.4: KMO and Bartlett's Test of Factors Influencing Property values in Gated Residential Estates

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.859
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1870.984
	Df	190
	Sig.	.000

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2025.

The results presented in Table 4.4 summarize the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, which assess the appropriateness of the dataset for factor analysis. The KMO value of 0.859 indicates a "meritorious" level of sampling adequacy, implying that the intercorrelations among the factors influencing property values in gated residential estates are sufficiently high for the data to be factorable. According to Kaiser's benchmark, values between 0.80 and 0.89 suggest that the variables share common variance and that the sample is adequate for extracting reliable underlying dimensions.

Table 4.5: Communalities of Factors Influencing Property values in Gated Residential Estates

Factors	Initial	Extraction
Controlled Access and Exclusive Services	1.000	.610
Higher demand for gated communities in urban areas	1.000	.697
Regulatory compliance in construction practices	1.000	.455
Socioeconomic Profile of Residents	1.000	.421
Supply and Demand Dynamics	1.000	.666
Design and Physical Characteristics of Properties	1.000	.721
Aesthetic Appeal and Environmental Quality	1.000	.739
Availability and Quality of Infrastructure	1.000	.746
Accessibility to major roads and public transportation networks	1.000	.792
Neighborhood Crime Rates	1.000	.696
Street and Road Conditions	1.000	.713
Flexibility in Land Use and Modifications	1.000	.777
Community Initiatives	1.000	.835
Public Infrastructure and Service Quality	1.000	.752
Higher Service Charges	1.000	.649
Perceived Social Status and Prestige	1.000	.622
Urban Planning and Land-Use Policies	1.000	.536
Availability of Technology and Connectivity	1.000	.587
Flood Risk and Climate Vulnerability	1.000	.251
Diversity and Heterogeneity of Residents	1.000	.766

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2025.

The results reveal that several variables demonstrate strong communalities, indicating high relevance within the factor structure. Community Initiatives (.835), Diversity and Heterogeneity of Residents (.766), Public Infrastructure and Service Quality (.752) and Availability and Quality of Infrastructure (.746) all exhibit high extraction values, underscoring their significance in shaping property values in gated residential environments. Moreover, the strong communalities for Street and Road Conditions (.713), Aesthetic Appeal and Environmental Quality (.739) and Design and Physical Characteristics of Properties (.721).

However, a few variables show relatively lower communalities, such as Flood Risk and Climate Vulnerability (.251), Socioeconomic Profile of Residents (.421) and Regulatory Compliance in Construction Practices (.455).

Table 4.6: Component Matrix^a of Factors Influencing the Property Values of Gated Residential Property Values

Factors	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Aesthetic Appeal and Environmental Quality	.851			
Flexibility in Land Use and Modifications	.835			
Availability and Quality of Infrastructure	.817			
Public Infrastructure and Service Quality	.815			
Higher Service Charges	.793			
Street and Road Conditions	.781			
Neighborhood Crime Rates	.761			
Design and Physical Characteristics of Properties	.731			
Community Initiatives	.724		-.547	
Accessibility to major roads and public transportation networks	.682			
Supply and Demand Dynamics	.623		-.504	
Regulatory compliance in construction practices				
Perceived Social Status and Prestige		.575		
Higher demand for gated communities in urban areas		-.569		
Availability of Technology and Connectivity		.563		
Urban Planning and Land-Use Policies		.542		
Controlled Access and Exclusive Services		-.511		
Flood Risk and Climate Vulnerability				
Socioeconomic Profile of Residents				
Diversity and Heterogeneity of Residents				.701

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2025.

Component 1 is the most dominant and represents a broad infrastructural and environmental quality dimension. It records high loadings for Aesthetic Appeal and Environmental Quality (.851), Flexibility in Land Use and Modifications (.835), Availability and Quality of Infrastructure (.817), Public Infrastructure and Service Quality (.815), Higher Service Charges

(.793), Street and Road Conditions (.781), Neighborhood Crime Rates (.761), Design and Physical Characteristics of Properties (.731), Community Initiatives (.724), Accessibility to Major Roads and Public Transportation (.682) and Supply and Demand Dynamics (.623).

Component 2 represents a socio-market and regulatory valuation dimension and includes Perceived Social Status and Prestige (.575), Availability of Technology and Connectivity (.563), Urban Planning and Land-Use Policies (.542) and Regulatory Compliance in Construction Practices, with Higher Demand for Gated Communities in Urban Areas and Controlled Access and Exclusive Services both displaying negative loadings (-.569 and -.511, respectively).

Component 3 presents a residual dimension and although its structure is weaker, it includes Community Initiatives (-.547) and Supply and Demand Dynamics (-.504) with moderate negative loadings. This suggests a potential divergence between community-driven activities and market forces, possibly implying that while communal engagement enhances livability, it may not directly align with investor priorities or short-term profitability expectations. Component 4 stands alone with only one significant variable: Diversity and Heterogeneity of Residents, which loads at .701.

Table 4.7: Rotated Component Matrix^a of Factors Influencing the Property Values of Gated Residential Property Values

Factors	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Community Initiatives	.902			
Public Infrastructure and Service Quality	.818			
Flexibility in Land Use and Modifications	.813			
Supply and Demand Dynamics	.798			
Design and Physical Characteristics of Properties	.773			
Aesthetic Appeal and Environmental Quality	.655			
Street and Road Conditions	.644			
Socioeconomic Profile of Residents				
Accessibility to major roads and public transportation networks		.813		
Controlled Access and Exclusive Services		.703		
Availability and Quality of Infrastructure		.678		
Neighborhood Crime Rates		.620		

Higher Service Charges	.561
Regulatory compliance in construction practices	
Availability of Technology and Connectivity	.741
Perceived Social Status and Prestige	.740
Urban Planning and Land-Use Policies	.699
Flood Risk and Climate Vulnerability	
Diversity and Heterogeneity of Residents	.867
Higher demand for gated communities in urban areas	.580

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2025.

Component 1 emerges as the most dominant and cohesive, representing a community-**integrated infrastructure and environmental value framework (IIEVF)**. It contains high loadings for Community Initiatives (.902), Public Infrastructure and Service Quality (.818), Flexibility in Land Use and Modifications (.813), Supply and Demand Dynamics (.798), Design and Physical Characteristics of Properties (.773), Aesthetic Appeal and Environmental Quality (.655) and Street and Road Conditions (.644).

Component 2, on the other hand, captures a cluster of **security and access-related infrastructure determinants (SAID)**. It features strong loadings for Accessibility to Major Roads and Public Transportation Networks (.813), Controlled Access and Exclusive Services (.703), Availability and Quality of Infrastructure (.678), Neighborhood Crime Rates (.620) and Higher Service Charges (.561). This factor can be interpreted as representing “Urban Mobility and Secured Premium Services.” Component 3 captures socio-technological prestige indicators and includes **Availability of Technology and Connectivity (ATC)** (.741), Perceived Social Status and Prestige (.740) and Urban Planning and Land-Use Policies (.699).

Component 4 contains only two strongly loaded variables: **Diversity and Heterogeneity of Residents (DHR)** (.867) and **Higher Demand for Gated Communities in Urban Areas (HDGC)** (.580). This factor appears to encapsulate socio-demographic dynamics and emergent market trends. Diversity represents the presence of mixed backgrounds economic, cultural, or professional within a residential enclave, while High Demand indicates escalating buyer interest in gated formats. Notably, several variables including Flood Risk and Climate Vulnerability, Regulatory Compliance in Construction Practices and Socioeconomic Profile of Residents did not load significantly on any component.

Table 4.8: Descriptive Analysis of the Factors Influencing Property values in Non-Gated Residential Estates

	Mean	Rank
Neighborhood Crime Rates	3.8718	1 st
Supply and Demand Dynamics	3.8269	2 nd
Socioeconomic Profile of Residents	3.6282	3 rd
Accessibility to major roads and public transportation networks	3.6218	4 th
Flood Risk and Climate Vulnerability	3.5577	5 th
Availability and Quality of Infrastructure	3.5385	6 th
Design and Physical Characteristics of Properties	3.5321	7 th
Community Initiatives	3.5000	8 th
Aesthetic Appeal and Environmental Quality	3.4808	9 th
Perceived Social Status and Prestige	3.4679	10 th
Availability of Technology and Connectivity	3.4487	11 th
Public Infrastructure and Service Quality	3.4423	12 th
Urban Planning and Land-Use Policies	3.4359	13 th
Diversity and Heterogeneity of Residents	3.4167	14 th
Controlled Access and Exclusive Services	3.4103	15 th
Higher Service Charges	3.3974	16 th
Flexibility in Land Use and Modifications	3.3590	17 th
Regulatory compliance in construction practices	3.3397	18 th
Street and Road Conditions	3.2949	19 th
Higher demand for gated communities in urban areas	3.2179	20 th

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2025.

The top-ranked factor, neighborhood crime rates (mean = 3.8718). Abere, Ogunba and Dugeri (2020) mirrors recent findings in Southwestern Nigeria where established that safety of property titles and general environmental security are major concerns limiting investment in the real estate sector. Closely following crime is the factor of supply and demand dynamics (mean = 3.8269), which illustrates the classic economic principle that property values are influenced by the interplay between availability and buyer interest. The third factor, socioeconomic profile of residents (mean = 3.6282), points to how resident income levels, education, employment type and social behavior patterns influence property values.

The accessibility to major roads and public transport networks (mean = 3.6218) ranks fourth and reveals the practical importance of urban connectivity in real estate valuation. In fifth place, flood risk and climate vulnerability (mean = 3.5577) demonstrate increasing buyer sensitivity to environmental sustainability and physical safety. The sixth-ranked factor, availability and quality of infrastructure (mean = 3.5385), reflects the foundational importance of reliable utilities such as electricity, potable water, drainage systems and broadband access in determining livability and property value.

The design and physical characteristics of properties (mean = 3.5321), ranked seventh, pertain to factors such as layout, ventilation, aesthetic finishing and architectural conformity. Community initiatives (mean = 3.5000), including neighborhood watch programs, sanitation drives and communal improvement efforts, appear in eighth place. The aesthetic appeal and environmental quality (mean = 3.4808). Ranked tenth, perceived social status and prestige (mean = 3.4679) suggests that while reputation and symbolic value still influence buyer decisions, they are not the primary valuation drivers in non-gated estates. At eleventh place, availability of technology and connectivity (mean = 3.4487) reveals a growing awareness of digital infrastructure in real estate valuation.

The twelfth-ranked factor, public infrastructure and service quality (mean = 3.4423), reflects public investments in amenities such as police stations, schools, public health centers and waste disposal systems. Urban planning and land-use policies rank thirteenth with a mean score of 3.4359. In fourteenth place is the diversity and heterogeneity of residents (mean = 3.4167), which implies that ethnically or socioeconomically mixed communities do not significantly influence property values in Abuja's non-gated estates. Controlled access and exclusive services (mean = 3.4103), ranked fifteenth. In sixteenth place, higher service charges (mean = 3.3974) show that additional costs for waste collection, security levies, or estate maintenance deter buyers.

Flexibility in land use and modifications (mean = 3.3590), ranked seventeenth, reflects a moderate appreciation for the ability to adapt structures for commercial or mixed-use purposes. Eighteenth on the list is regulatory compliance in construction practices (mean = 3.3397). Street and road conditions (mean = 3.2949), ranked nineteenth. Finally, higher demand for gated communities in urban areas (mean = 3.2179) ranks lowest, confirming that the existence of gated alternatives does not significantly devalue properties in non-gated estates.

Table 4.9: KMO and Bartlett's Test of Factors Influencing Property values in Non-Gated Residential Estates

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.855
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2793.493
	Df	190
	Sig.	.000

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2025.

The KMO value of **0.855** indicates a “meritorious” level of sampling adequacy, implying that the inter-correlations among the factors influencing property values in non-gated residential estates are sufficiently high for the data to be factorable. According to Kaiser’s benchmark, values between 0.80 and 0.89 suggest that the variables share common variance and that the sample is adequate for extracting reliable underlying dimensions.

Table 4.10: Communalities of Factors Influencing Property values in Non-Gated Residential Estates

Factors	Initial	Extraction
Controlled Access and Exclusive Services	1.000	.579
Higher demand for gated communities in urban areas	1.000	.763
Regulatory compliance in construction practices	1.000	.785
Socioeconomic Profile of Residents	1.000	.688
Supply and Demand Dynamics	1.000	.631
Design and Physical Characteristics of Properties	1.000	.787
Aesthetic Appeal and Environmental Quality	1.000	.808
Availability and Quality of Infrastructure	1.000	.718
Accessibility to major roads and public transportation networks	1.000	.709
Neighborhood Crime Rates	1.000	.634
Street and Road Conditions	1.000	.784
Flexibility in Land Use and Modifications	1.000	.780
Community Initiatives	1.000	.773
Public Infrastructure and Service Quality	1.000	.803
Higher Service Charges	1.000	.713
Perceived Social Status and Prestige	1.000	.754
Urban Planning and Land-Use Policies	1.000	.819
Availability of Technology and Connectivity	1.000	.823
Flood Risk and Climate Vulnerability	1.000	.788

Diversity and Heterogeneity of Residents	1.000	.627
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Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2025.

The highest communalities were recorded for availability of technology and connectivity (0.823), urban planning and land-use policies (0.819) and public infrastructure and service quality (0.803), underscoring their critical underlying influence on property valuation. Also ranking highly are aesthetic appeal and environmental quality (0.808), design and physical characteristics (0.787), flood risk and climate vulnerability (0.788) and street and road conditions (0.784), indicating the increasing relevance of physical and environmental integrity in buyer decision-making.

Mid-range communalities were observed in variables like flexibility in land use and modifications (0.780), regulatory compliance in construction practices (0.785), community initiatives (0.773), higher demand for gated communities (0.763) and perceived social status and prestige (0.754). Lower but still relevant communalities were recorded for socioeconomic profile of residents (0.688), supply and demand dynamics (0.631), neighborhood crime rates (0.634) and diversity and heterogeneity of residents (0.627), indicating these factors have a consistent, though more moderate, impact on underlying property value structures.

Table 4.11: Component Matrix^a of Factors Influencing the Property Values of Non-Gated Residential Property Values

Factors	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Aesthetic Appeal and Environmental Quality	.881			
Public Infrastructure and Service Quality	.851			
Higher Service Charges	.830			
Availability of Technology and Connectivity	.823			
Higher demand for gated communities in urban areas	.793			
Socioeconomic Profile of Residents	.788			
Flexibility in Land Use and Modifications	.787			
Street and Road Conditions	.765			
Neighborhood Crime Rates	.742			
Community Initiatives	.739			

Flood Risk and Climate Vulnerability	.712	-.524
Design and Physical Characteristics of Properties	.706	
Regulatory compliance in construction practices	.685	
Accessibility to major roads and public transportation networks	.677	
Urban Planning and Land-Use Policies	.651	.587
Availability and Quality of Infrastructure	.611	
Diversity and Heterogeneity of Residents	.560	
Controlled Access and Exclusive Services		
Perceived Social Status and Prestige	.541	.614
Supply and Demand Dynamics		.561

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2025.

The first component such as aesthetic appeal and environmental quality (.881), public infrastructure and service quality (.851), higher service charges (.830), availability of technology and connectivity (.823), higher demand for gated communities (.793), socioeconomic profile of residents (.788), flexibility in land use and modifications (.787), street and road conditions (.765), neighborhood crime rates (.742) and community initiatives (.739) all load highly onto Component 1.

The loading of higher service charges (.830) alongside desirable traits also implies a readiness among buyers to accept higher costs when justified by commensurate service. Component 2 introduces a contrasting dimension that appears to reflect policy sensitivity and environmental risk consciousness, marked primarily by flood risk and climate vulnerability loading at .712 but negatively associated with -.524 on urban planning and land-use policies (.587) and perceived social status and prestige (.614), the latter also partially loading on Component 3.

Component 3 appears less densely populated but carries conceptual weight, representing market mechanics and economic rationality. Here, supply and demand dynamics (.561) is the central variable, with secondary overlap from urban planning and prestige. Component 4 is notably less saturated but reveals subtleties in the data, showing minor overlap in urban planning and perceived prestige, while most other variables do not load meaningfully. The low prominence of diversity and heterogeneity of residents (.560) in the component matrix further suggests that demographic plurality.

Table 4.12: Rotated Component Matrix^a of Factors Influencing the Property Values of Non-Gated Residential Property Values

Factors	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Flood Risk and Climate Vulnerability	.848			
Flexibility in Land Use and Modifications	.826			
Design and Physical Characteristics of Properties	.823			
Community Initiatives	.811			
Public Infrastructure and Service Quality	.792			
Socioeconomic Profile of Residents	.724			
Aesthetic Appeal and Environmental Quality	.672	.557		
Neighborhood Crime Rates	.506			
Regulatory compliance in construction practices		.850		
Controlled Access and Exclusive Services		.753		
Availability of Technology and Connectivity		.743		
Higher demand for gated communities in urban areas		.741		
Street and Road Conditions		.675		
Accessibility to major roads and public transportation networks		.589		
Higher Service Charges	.543	.552		
Perceived Social Status and Prestige			.796	
Urban Planning and Land-Use Policies			.795	
Availability and Quality of Infrastructure			.734	
Supply and Demand Dynamics				.759
Diversity and Heterogeneity of Residents				.520

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2025.

Component 1 emerges as the most robust dimension, dominated by eight variables that reflect what may be interpreted as a "**Sustainable Livability and Infrastructure Quality**" (SLIQ) construct. This component includes flood risk and climate vulnerability (.848), flexibility in land use and modifications (.826), design and physical characteristics of properties (.823), community initiatives (.811), public infrastructure and service quality (.792), socioeconomic profile of residents (.724), aesthetic appeal and environmental quality (.672) and neighborhood crime rates (.506). Component 2 presents a cluster of variables associated with "**Controlled Access, Technological Modernity and Regulatory Assurance**" (CATMRA), with strong loadings on regulatory compliance in construction practices (.850), controlled access and exclusive services (.753), availability of technology and connectivity (.743), higher demand

for gated communities in urban areas (.741), street and road conditions (.675) and accessibility to major roads and public transportation networks (.589).

Component 3 reflects what can be described as a "**Prestige and Policy-Driven Environment**" (**PPDE**) component, featuring strong loadings on perceived social status and prestige (.796), urban planning and land-use policies (.795) and availability and quality of infrastructure (.734). Component 4 is comparatively narrower but points to a "**Market Dynamics and Social Composition**" (**MDSC**) cluster, led by supply and demand dynamics (.759) and diversity and heterogeneity of residents (.520).

5.0 CONCLUSION

The findings clearly establish that gated estates are distinguished by their structured infrastructure, high security, integrated community features and stronger valuation outcomes, particularly among Two and Three-Bedroom Flats. These estates tend to attract higher-income, educated and professionally stable residents who value exclusivity, safety and premium amenities. In contrast, non-gated estates exhibit greater variability in infrastructure quality and demographic diversity. While more affordable and accessible, these estates also face challenges related to infrastructural inconsistency, limited planning oversight and lower valuation stability though they are evolving with rising expectations for security, regulation and digital access. The divergence in physical characteristics and socioeconomic compositions between both estate types directly influences how property values are perceived and determined.

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